

ROV Video Recording Best Practices

Technical Guidelines for Future-Proof Seafloor Imaging

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1. DOCUMENT DETAILS

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Important Note: This document was created from an end-user perspective, as guidance to ROV operators and data managers, who may not be aware of all potential 'end-uses'. Conversely there may be operational experiences not included in the document.

Summary: The document summarizes experience from extensive ROV video processing in relation to the EMINENT-project and DeepSee projects.

Version History:

- Version 1.0 created prior to the EMINENT DeepInsight cruise 2025
- Version 1.1 was created based on the experiences from the EMINENT Deep Insight 2025 cruise, including extensive experiments with technical aspects of ROV video-filming, camera set up etc.

1.a. Suggestions and Revisions

This document is meant to be live, in the form that it will be updated with version tracking as experience expands or new functions are added. If you find topics in this document that needs revision, please send us an email and these will be considered into revised versions.

TECHNICAL GUIDELINES

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2. INTRODUCTION

Acquiring seafloor video imagery is a capital-intensive endeavor. The ROV camera serves as the ‘sharp end’ of a substantial logistical operation, involving specialized vessels and extensive personnel. It is therefore imperative that this significant investment is leveraged to its full potential, ensuring the maximum possible utility is derived from the data—both for the immediate stakeholders and the society funding the work.

Advanced ROVs, such as the Ægir6000, have amazing capabilities. Some involve the cameras, some involve its sensors and other involve its sampling capacity. Sometimes there are tradeoffs between using these functions, and priorities to be made. This manual or set of recommendations can be worthwhile reading even if the main mission of the dive is sampling, as one generally always wants good images of what is sampled. We thus recommend spending some time getting reasonably good filming AROUND the object before the sampling.

A second tradeoff is time spent filming objects of special interest and progress on the filming covering the most possible area. It is natural that once one ‘finally’ reaches an object of special interest, that the ROV pilot spends time adoring that object. ‘Adoring’ and detailed evaluation is best done after filming, and the focus should thus be to get the best images, filming from different angles without zooming, and then to move on.

2.a. The Importance of Future-Proofing

A substantial section of this document is about how to ‘future-proof’ the video. **It cannot be stressed strongly enough that the key analysis of the video-imagery comes after, and not during the filming.** For that reason, one needs to systematically assure that the imagery is ready for this work.

No human brain can intuitively create the 3D photomosaic/photogrammetry with mm-resolution that a computer can construct if the video is filmed correctly. The future will hold more computerized techniques for video analysis and thus the filming should be done in ways that do not hinder such analysis. This goes also for ROV pilots not familiar with these computational techniques. Thus, protocols should be followed.

These guidelines are not merely general best practices but are driven by modern technologies such as **Machine Learning (e.g., YOLO models for object and life form detection) and Photogrammetry**. These methods allow us to create additional value, data, and information from ROV video that otherwise just land in storage. By following these protocols, we transform video from passive archives into active data sources for quantitative analysis.

2.b. Data Management Standards

A second part of ensuring that the ROV-filming is ‘future-proof’ is that video material is stored in correct format, with standardized file and folder names and that position and other metadata follow a standardized format.

On board it might not seem relevant if there is a space or underscore in a filename, or text or if positions follow one or another format. Nevertheless, such details can truly cost days if not weeks of extra labor on shore as all material may need to be restructured or re-written. **We strongly recommend that a standardized protocol is followed on these topics to all levels of detail, and no matter who is handling the data.** There is no room for personal or institutional opinion on these matters once a protocol is established. At the very least all Ægir6000 video material should follow a standardized protocol.

i Note

Note that this document is based on experience with the Ægir6000 ROV operated by UiB. Most recommendations will be relevant for any ROV operation.

3. FUTURE-PROOF ROV VIDEO RECORDING

Key goals of ROV video recording include both understanding the present and presenting a baseline for the future. Nature is dynamic, changes due to cyclic or chaotic variations or stress, whereof some are natural, some are secondary effects of human activity (e.g. climate) and others are direct effects of human activity. Fishing, mining, cabling, research etc. Regardless of the reason for change we want accurate data for how things are to evaluate how they change.

Creating such a baseline of seafloor images demands good protocol, both for technical details, storage of files, and how objects or seafloor is filmed.

We already have recordings of the same sponges or seafloor structures (such as ripples) years apart and can document how they evolve. For someone, years or generations, into the future to be able to use our work we need to be consistent in how it is obtained. This document is meant to help 'future-proof' this work. **A very important part of this is to allow for 3D photogrammetry of a given feature of interest.** We are convinced that in the future the most valued parts of today's work is where we have obtained detailed overlapping filming of a feature from many angles. The method is described below, but can be boiled down to filming an object from many sides without zooming and without any tools in the frame.

3.a. Dual or Multi-Purpose Recording

Most of the ROV time can be used for dual, or even multipurpose science. It is important that the ROV pilot is aware of the many uses of the video-footage and allows time to record the images other sciences might need. In particular we note that **sampling processes are small scale examples of human alteration of the seafloor**, and it is important not just to sample but also to record the before and after scenarios. There are many examples of this, but in short the lesson is to film a sampling area also after the samples are collected.

Figure 1: Example from the Mareano 2025 cruise: Images recorded seconds apart allow for advanced oceanographic evaluation.

Example from the Mareano 2025 cruise: Images recorded seconds apart allow for advanced oceanographic evaluation on plume behaviour, currents and particle settlement velocity. However, this demands that the ROV keeps filming the same site until the plume has settled. Furthermore, the sampling site could ideally have been covered by before and after transects to evaluate the effect of the dense plume.

4. TECHNICAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FILES, BITRATES AND RESOLUTIONS

4.a. Master Object and Synchronization

A critical aspect of multi-camera operations is defining the “Master Object” for synchronization.

1. **Master Camera (Preferred):** Ideally, recordings are synchronized such that all cameras share the same start and stop times (or are triggered by a master timecode). This produces files of identical length and coverage. This setup allows analysts to easily switch between views (e.g., forward vs. downward) at any specific moment, facilitating rapid and accurate interpretation.
2. **Dive Duration as Master (Problematic):** Sometimes the “dive duration” is treated as the master object, while individual cameras record independently with varying durations and inconsistent overlap (especially when they have different resolutions). This fragmentation makes post-processing analysis significantly more difficult, as correlating events across unaligned video files becomes a manual and error-prone task.

Recommendation: Prioritize systems where all active cameras are **triggered simultaneously** to produce perfectly aligned files.

4.b. File and Folder Naming and Structure

When video material is stored for later use, it is critical to use a consistent naming convention and folder structure. This ensures compatibility with automated ingestion tools, cloud backups (e.g., GCP, AWS S3, Azure Blob Storage), and future data processing pipelines.

Key Principles: 1. **No Spaces or Special Characters:** Strictly avoid spaces, parentheses (), brackets [], or ampersands &. These often cause failures in scripts (Python, Bash), command-line tools, and web-based storage viewers. Use underscores _ or hyphens - as separators. 2. **Lowercase Only:** Do not use uppercase letters. Filesystems (especially Linux/Unix-based) are case-sensitive, and mixing cases leads to errors. 3. **Standardized Hierarchy:** Follow a strict excursion -> dive -> file structure.

4.b.i. *Filename Convention:* **Recommended Format:** `yyyymmdd-hhmmss_cameraid`

Example: `20250929-162359_cam1.mp4`

4.b.ii. *Folder Structure:* **Recommended Hierarchy:**

1. **Root Folder (excursion name):** Top-level folder named after the campaign or excursion.
2. **Dive Folder:** Subfolders for each specific dive.
3. **Video Files:** Contained within the dive folder.

Example Structure: `- excursion_name/ - dive_01/ - 20250929-162359_cam1.mp4 - dive_02/ - ...`

Forbidden Characters

Folder and filenames must NOT contain square brackets [] (often used for metadata like [Dive 1]) or spaces. These characters “break” many storage services and script-based access. Always use lowercase alphanumeric characters and underscores/hyphens.

Use standardized readme text files in folders explaining the content of folders.

4.c. *File Formats*

Ideal file formats include:

1. **MP4 with H.264 encoding** (Preferred)
2. **MPG**
3. **MKV**

Explanation: Preferred video format is MP4 with H.264 encoding. MP4 files can be played in any modern player, including web browsers, and allow for very fast seeking. Videos of any other format are therefore converted into MP4 before use.

Avoid H.265 (HEVC)

While H.265 offers better compression, it is **not recommended** for general delivery because many web browsers and operating systems do not support it out of the box. Using H.265 often forces users to install specific codecs or perform time-consuming transcoding before the video can be viewed or processed.

For outdated formats such as AVI and MOV, this conversion process takes quite a bit of computational time. Other formats, such as MPG and especially MKV, allow for demuxing if they internally contain the right kind of file. This is super-fast and not problematic. The reason MPG and MKV formats are often used is likely that they are more robust regarding unexpected technical issues

than straight MP4. So, both MPG and MKV are acceptable formats to use if MP4 can be extracted by demuxing rather than re-encoding. FPS and especially bitrates should be kept reasonable so that normal computers can handle them (see below).

4.d. Bit-Rates and Frames Per Second (fps)

Standard cinematic and broadcast video typically utilizes frame rates of 24 to 30 fps. While this ensures a smooth viewing experience, it results in high bit-rates which, particularly at high resolutions, can lead to data management challenges or recording failures.

Most of the actual post-processing is based on still images, so it is far more important to get good high-quality images than lots of high-speed filming. We typically use only 1 to 2 frames per second in our post-processing work. Hence, **having two good quality still images per second would likely be the better option** than 30 fps where the individual frames exhibit compression artifacts and motion blur.

While the output could technically be a simple image sequence, this would result in a difficult to manage number of individual files. A practical compromise is to merge these high-quality stills into a 'pseudo video' (a low-FPS video file), maintaining individual frame quality while keeping file management simple. The final verdict on the optimal format might evolve, but currently, this balance might serve best.

4.e. Resolution

4K has higher resolution than HD, and we suggest that it is used especially for still images, where possible. As for post-processing of video it would be sufficient with **one or two frames per second of 4K resolution still images**.

5. TECHNICAL DETAILS: ROV SETUP

5.a. Laser Dots

For tilted scenes 2 laser dots are not enough, and one would need **at least 3 (better with 4+) laser points, ideally a whole grid**, to evaluate size and thus distance. The distance between the laser dots should always be recorded in the metadata.

Warning

Note: It is very difficult to automatically extract laser point locations from images. Additionally, the laser points disturb e.g. object/life form recognition. So ideally only a subsection of the frames would have laser points, e.g. if the still image approach is chosen then only one frame per second would have the laser pointers.

5.b. Stereo-Filming

Filming with two cameras that are set as filming parallel and have the same camera angle allows for evaluating size and distance in post-processing. These cameras should be separated approximately between **1/20 and 1/30 of the distance to the object**.

Experience with the 2025 UiB/EMINENT ROV survey demonstrated that **it is extremely difficult to set up two individual cameras that are not prefabricated for stereo filming**. The camera/lens specs need to be exactly the same, they need to be 100% parallel and they need to be configured to have one light sensor for both cameras etc.

6. INFORMATION FOLLOWING THE VIDEO IN SEPARATE FILES

6.a. Metadata Requirements

Essential metadata includes:

- **Location (x,y,z):** Pitch, roll, heading, altitude, ideally of the camera(s) and not just the ROV
- **UTM:** Must be denoted with **at least one digit** behind the decimal sign to ensure <1m resolution. ALWAYS note UTM zone in metadata.
- **Lat/Long:** MUST be recorded with **at least five decimals of a degree.**
 - *Note:* In our primary operating area (Northeast Atlantic: Jan Mayen to Svalbard), a precision of 5 decimal places provides ~1.1m resolution in Latitude and ~0.3-0.5m in Longitude. This roughly aligns with the 1m precision target of the UTM formatting.
- **Distance to the object/surface** that is filmed would be useful, but we assume that is not an option (could be computed in a stereo camera setup) or recorded with dedicated sensors
- **Camera specifications:** Describe camera lenses (focal length, field of view) and zoom states. Explicit lens data is preferred, though high-quality video allows photogrammetry to derive it automatically.
- **Laser dot spacing:** Distance between laser dots, with highest possible measured precision
- **Readme files:** Use standardized readme text files in folders explaining the content of folders

! Critical: Metadata Synchronization

Accurate time and date information is absolutely essential for both the video files and accompanying metadata. Both must use synchronized, high-precision timestamps to enable:

- Reliable correlation between video frames and positional/sensor data
- Multi-camera alignment and cross-referencing
- Future reprocessing and analysis workflows

Recommendation: Use GPS-synchronized clocks for all recording systems. The metadata file and video file timestamps must be verifiably aligned.

Optional Overlay Version: For operational reference, consider producing a **second version** of the main camera video with metadata (time, position, depth) burnt into the frame. This overlay version aids quick correlation during analysis but should be clearly labeled as a reference copy. The **primary archive version should remain clean** (no overlays) to preserve maximum image quality for photogrammetry and machine learning applications.

6.b. Other Information

6.b.i. Dive Documentation:

- Purpose of dive
- Technical/instrumental issues or challenges
- Notes on both technical (time of active zooming) and scientific issues
- Use a timelog to tie notes to video
- Explain shortly what is done, even if it is apparently evident for those involved at the time
- Also explain what might not be done, e.g. reasons for pauses, technical issues and the like
- If abbreviations or acronyms are used, then explain these and be consistent

i Note

No human can in real time digest and take notes on all the biological and geological observations that occur as the ROV passes by. In many cases it is best to accept that true visual analysis comes after the video recording (in reality on land), and for that reason a short note like 'bio-highlight', or 'nudibranch' is enough. Thus, keep notes short and focus on progress with the filming.

7. NOTES FOR THE ACTUAL FILMING

7.a. ROV Track Planning and High-Resolution Bathymetry

When planning ROV dive transects, consult available bathymetric data for the survey area. **If high-resolution bathymetry (e.g., 1m or finer) is available nearby, the ROV track should ideally cover the high-resolution bathymetry area.** This provides several advantages:

1. **Ground-truthing:** ROV video can validate and interpret features visible in the high-res bathymetry
2. **Precise positioning:** High-res bathymetry enables better correlation between video observations and mapped seafloor features
3. **Enhanced photogrammetry:** Having an independent bathymetric reference improves 3D reconstruction accuracy
4. **Scientific value:** Combining video with high-res bathymetry maximizes the interpretive power of both datasets

Coordinate dive planning with available bathymetric surveys to ensure maximum overlap where high-resolution data exists.

7.b. Filming Strategy

On flat seafloor it may work fine to film video transects along linear segments of a pre-decided length (e.g. 200 or 800 meters). This strategy is not ideal in rough terrain as a straight transect will involve filming lots of 'blue' water (distant seafloor) or filming terrain in obtuse angles.

For rough or steep terrain, it is our recommendation to **abandon the straight line filming dogma** and rather film a transect making sure that the lens is orthogonal (looking straight at) the terrain.

As repeated many times in this document, computerized post-processing will take over many tasks hitherto performed by humans. One such post-processing task will be to have the computer make 3D photomosaics out of the video images and then allow for true spatial grids to be placed on the filmed terrain allowing for true spatially consistent counting of e.g. benthos.

Figure 2: Regional photogrammetry of a slope with abundant sponges.

For example, regional photogrammetry of a slope with abundant sponges (see Figure 2) allows 2×2 m frames to be automatically placed on the photogrammetry, orthogonal to the seafloor regardless of its steepness. When zoomed in there is a mm-scale resolution of life and geology in each frame which can be studied and quantified/counted systematically along the seafloor slope. Biology is placed into habitat context, with directional components etc. (ROV video is from the NOD 2024 cruise. The method and its results were presented by Schmid et al., 2025, Deep Sea Mineral Conference 2025 in Bergen).

7.c. Camera Angle

Ideally, the camera should not look vertically down onto the seafloor, but be tilted forward (e.g. ~30°). This perspective provides depth cues essential for both human interpretation and 3D reconstruction.

This angle must be adjusted dynamically based on terrain: * **On flat terrain:** Maintain a slight forward tilt (avoid 90° down). * **On slopes:** The camera should look 'up' the slope. Just like on flat terrain, avoid looking orthogonal (perpendicular) to the seafloor. Instead, maintain the same ~30° **forward tilt relative to the slope** to provide perspective.

Key principles:

- It is best that as little of the frame is 'blue' or just water in the horizon. Try to fill most of the frame with the seafloor-geo/biology.
- It is important that filming is done as consistent as possible. Sometimes there may be a purpose of zooming but **zoom as little as possible**. If zoomed for some detail, consider setting back the camera angle to standard before moving onwards.
- If traversing along the contours of a slope, consider pointing the cameras so they still film more into the slope, if possible.

7.d. Lighting

One of the most crucial parameters. Ægir6000 usually gets it right. Other video material that we have access to has either too little or, even worse, **too much light**. Many of the life forms in the

deep sea, e.g. sponges, are white and appear as bright, unrecognizable blobs when too much light is used. This is particularly a problem when filming close.

Things that are a bit dark can be fixed post-processing if needed. Too much light cannot be fixed as there is 'no information'.

7.e. Sampling

When one chooses to sample either biology or geology it is presumably because there is something important. We strongly suggest that one video documents the sampled object carefully before it is sampled. This is best done following the 3-point protocol listed in the section below. In some cases it can be useful to document a before and after sampling situation. If so, repeat the 3-point protocol below after the sampling.

7.f. Dwelling/Resting While Discussing

Maximizing survey efficiency requires balancing detailed observation with area coverage. While it is natural to pause and observe interesting features during operations, prolonged dwelling significantly reduces the total area surveyed. Detailed analysis and discussion are often better performed during post-processing, where imagery can be reviewed without time constraints.

We therefore recommend prioritizing data acquisition—either by filming features from multiple angles (see protocol below) or continuing the transect—rather than holding a stationary view for extended periods. If a feature warrants detailed inspection, active filming provides more value than a static hover.

7.f.i. Recommended Protocol for Dwelling: If one chooses to dwell on a feature that is interesting or important we recommend the following protocol:

1. **Choose a relevant zoom/camera angle and then stop zooming** at least for a while
2. **Get video footage of the object from as many sides as possible** by moving the camera, or the ROV sideways and up and down, keeping the object in view
3. **This procedure (and only this non-zoom procedure) allows for 3D photogrammetry** of the object with extreme (mm) resolution

Figure 3: *Ideal filming pattern for photogrammetry.*

The ideal filming pattern ensures that a feature of interest is filmed from multiple angles with significant overlap. If there are gaps between the filming it cannot be used, thus ensure plenty of overlap so that a feature of interest is filmed from multiple angles.

This filming pattern is also suggested as a pause or dwelling pattern for filming. In short, when in doubt, discussing or resting, progress slowly while passing the ROV sideways back and forth. The pattern may not make sense for those filming, but allows for spectacular post-processing.

Figure 4: Map with ROV tracks from the EMINENT DeepInsight 2025 cruise.

Note that during the EMINENT DeepInsight 2025 several different patterns for wide areal filming were tested, including multiple parallel ROV-tracks. This method should in theory give a good coverage, but turned out to result in gaps with no filming between lines. **If this approach is chosen, significant overlap MUST be prioritized rather than maximum area coverage.**

In cases where there is a pause in filming for other reasons than ‘something cool’, for example discussion ‘what is next’, we recommend **slowly moving the ROV sideways a few meters, then upwards and back to the original point but slightly above.** Repeat if more time. Move the ROV relatively little, so that each filmed strip of seafloor overlaps with the past. This resting pattern with overlapping strips of video filming allows for post-processing of video/photogrammetry where all the filmed area is joined into one 3D photomosaic.

7.g. Marine Snow

If there is lots of particles in the water, for example marine snow typical for June-September, then try to **choose camera angles that get as little snow in the frames as possible.** This can mean shorter distance to objects filmed and less horizon.

7.h. Special Needs for Photogrammetry

Critical requirements for successful photogrammetry:

1. **Zooming makes photogrammetry impossible.** If the zoom is used, mark it in notes following the file.
2. **No tools or ROV parts in the frame:** Filming with ROV tools must be cut away.

3. **No plumes from sampling or the like:** This has to be cut away.
4. **Keep consistent distance to objects filmed, and constant speed.**
5. **For areas of particular importance:** Film from different sides.
6. **For areas where one needs a wider perspective:** Ensure that each strip of filmed seafloor overlaps ideally with about $\frac{1}{4}$ image width. Gaps between filmed seafloor makes stitching of the mosaic impossible.

7.i. How Photogrammetry Works

An object of interest, in our case seafloor biology or geology, is filmed from many sides without zooming and with no disturbing objects (ROV tools). The video sequence can then be used to create a high resolution 3D model of the object of interest.

Figure 5: Basic illustration of how photogrammetry works. Illustration from: <https://thehaskinssociety.wildapricot.org/photogrammetry>

7.i.i. *Example: Seamount Slope Photogrammetry:* Photogrammetry of a seamount slope (see Figure 6) where the trace of images above the outcrop show the ROV flight track, and how 2D images are stitched into 3D photomosaics. (Video from the NOD 2024 cruise)

Figure 6: Seamount slope photogrammetry.

8. EXAMPLES AND CASE STUDIES

8.a. Example: Dense Sponge Coverage

Photogrammetry of an area with dense coverage of foliated sponges. Each individual sponge is resolved to a sub-cm resolution, allowing for close examination of their 3D structure, and return in the future evaluating how the ecosystem evolves. (Photogrammetry based on video from the EMINENT DeepInsight 2025 cruise)

Figure 7: Dense sponge coverage.

8.b. Example: Active Hydrothermal Vent (MAREANO 2025)

A very nice example of an active hydrothermal vent filmed on the MAREANO 2025 cruise. The total video sequence is 2¼ hours long. Most of the time is spent sampling and measuring the vent, but there are no images surveying the vent structure without tools in the frame.

Figure 8: Active hydrothermal vent (MAREANO 2025).

Warning

Missed Opportunity: Had one spent some minutes filming the vent, without any zooming and without tools, before starting to sample then one could have created a detailed (sub-cm resolution) 3D model of the vent and measured the flow rate. This could have contributed both to present research and documented the life of this highly dynamic structure.

8.c. Example: Jøtul Active Vent (EMINENT 2025)

An example of the Jøtul active vent, filmed on the EMINENT 2025 cruise. 3D photogrammetry allows for reconstruction of the vent-structure and the ventilating fluid flow. The video sequence is not ideal, and more time could have been spent on either side of the structure, but since there was no zooming and no tools in the frames the 3D model can be created.

Figure 9: *Jøtul active vent (EMINENT 2025).*

9. SUMMARY OF KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

💡 Quick Reference Checklist

Technical Setup:

- Use MP4 with H.264 encoding (avoid H.265)
- 1-2 fps of 4K resolution is sufficient (Pseudo-video)
- At least 3-4 laser points (ideally a grid)
- Record laser dot spacing in metadata

Metadata:

- Lat/Long with at least 5 decimal places (~1m resolution in NE Atlantic)
- UTM with at least 1 decimal place and zone notation
- Camera specifications (lens/FOV) and zoom states
- Time-stamped dive logs

Filming Protocol:

- **Camera Angle:** Default ~30° forward tilt. On slopes, look “up slope” (still ~30° relative tilt); avoid orthogonal/vertical views.
- **Dwelling:** Prioritize multi-angle active filming over static hovering.
- Minimize water/horizon in frame
- **Avoid zooming**
- Keep consistent distance and speed
- No tools/ROV parts in photogrammetry frames
- Document before and after sampling

Data Management:

- Standardized filenames (yyyymmdd-hhmmss_cameraid) and folder structure (excursion/dive_01/...)
- **Strictly lowercase**, no spaces or special characters
- Readme files in all folders
- Consistent protocols regardless of operator

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